

Optimisation protocol for 1kSA

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1. Sample quality evaluation

1.1 DNA purity:

DNA purity is measured by Nanodrop (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) and evaluated according to the following guidelines.

Absorbance	Ideal values	Acceptable range
A260 /A280	>1.8	1.75 - 2.0
A260 /A230	>1.9	1.85 - 2.2

1.2 DNA quantity:

DNA quantity is measured by Nanodrop (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) and Qubit dsDNA HS (high sensitivity) Assay Kit on the Qubit Fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA)

Notes:

- Typically, the Nanodrop significantly overestimates the DNA quantity.
- Qubit and Nanodrop values are broadly similar for samples with optimal DNA quality.
- The DNA required to build an LSK/NBD library depends on the DNA fragment size and distribution.

1.3 DNA integrity:

1.3.1 Agarose gel image

Agarose gel electrophoresis provides a useful indication of the DNA fragment size.

Extracted gDNA is run on a 0.7% agarose gel with a [Lambda DNA/HindIII Marker](#) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA; SM010).

1.3.2 Size distribution

A more accurate measure of DNA integrity requires an Agilent Fragment Analyzer, TapeStation or Femto Pulse System. In this case, the [TapeStation 4150 instrument](#) (Agilent, USA) was used with the Genomic DNA ScreenTape following instructions provided by the manufacturer.

Notes:

- The TapeStation instrument provides an estimation of the size distribution of DNA fragments using the [Genomic DNA ScreenTape](#).
NOTE: From practical experience, we have noted that ONT sequencing N50 for fragment sizes in the 15-60 kb range can be overestimated by up to 2-2.2.5 fold. For more accurate sizing of larger fragments above 50 kb, the Agilent Fragment analyzer or Femto Pulse Systems (Agilent, USA) may be more appropriate.
- TapeStation results are used to determine the approximate number of molecules in the sample.
- Ideally, 300-500 fmol DNA is used as starting material for library building to produce a library sufficient for 3 x 50 fmol loads on a PromethION flow cell.

1.3.3 TapeStation size distribution:

- The optimal DNA fragment size distribution for NBD and LSK library building is 15-35 kb.
- Important to note is that the TapeStation may overestimate the size of fragments >15 kb. Therefore, a mean input gDNA fragment size >50 kb (based on the TapeStation analysis) is recommended to obtain larger N50 sequencing values.

1.3.4 Short fragment depletion:

- Short fragments can be depleted. However, this may significantly reduce the amount of DNA available for library building.
- Starting material should be at least twice the amount required for library building to compensate for potential losses during the short fragment depletion process.
- To remove fragments <10 kb: [PacBio Short Read Eliminator \(SRE\) XS Kit](#)
- To remove fragments <25 kb: [Nanopore Short Fragment Eliminator Kit](#)

2. Shearing of DNA

If the size distribution of the input gDNA is >60 kb as measured on the TapeStation, the fragment size can be reduced to the range of 35-50 kb using one of the following methods.

Caution!

Shearing requires a conservative approach. It is recommended to follow the basic shearing protocol and add additional step-wise rounds of shearing if required to obtain the optimal mean fragment length. Checking the size distribution using the TapeStation or appropriate analysis method is recommended before commencing with an additional round of shearing.

2.1 Mechanical shearing using glass beads:

The mechanical shearing protocol is based on the Oxford Nanopore protocol <https://nanoporetech.com/document/extraction-method/fastprep-96>

UPGL modifications:

2.1.1 Materials:

- [Monarch® DNA Capture Beads](#) (T3005L - New England Biolabs, USA)
- [2 ml Eppendorf® LoBind tube](#) (0030108078 - Eppendorf)
- Sterile tweezers
- [Eppendorf Thermomixer® C](#)

2.1.2 Protocol:

- Add 1,000 ng DNA with a final volume of 50 µl to a 2 ml LoBind tube
- Add one glass bead per tube
- Place on Thermomixer at 1,000 rpm at 22°C
 - The number of cycles depends on DNA size and may require optimisation.
 - One cycle represents 1 minute of mixing followed by one minute of rest.
 - The standard protocol to reduce >60 kb DNA to ~20-30 kb is five cycles.

2.1.3 Quality check:

Following each shearing step, the DNA size and distribution are evaluated using the TapeStation or appropriate analysis method. Repeat shearing as needed until the desired size is reached.

2.1.4 DNA cleanup:

If DNA concentration is too low for the library building protocol, the DNA can be concentrated using one of the following methods.

- For DNA fragments that are in the optimal range and have no significant number of short fragments, use one of the following methods:
 - Reduce the DNA volume with a SpeedVac vacuum system until the required volume and concentration have been obtained.
 - Concentrate the DNA using the [Genomic DNA Clean & Concentrator kit](#) (D4010 - Zymo Research, USA). Elute DNA from the column using the supplied elution buffer preheated to 60°C.

- If a significant number of shorter fragments are present, proceed with short fragment elimination using one of the methods specified in 1.3.4.

2.2 Enzymatic shearing using the Shearase™ Plus enzyme:

2.2.1 Materials:

- [dsDNA Shearase™ Plus](#) (E2018-50 - Zymo Research, USA)
- Thermocycler
- 0.2 ml thin-walled tubes

2.2.2 Protocol:

- Standard reaction is performed in 10 µl containing
 - 5× Shearase buffer: 2 µl
 - Shearase enzyme: 0.4 µl (0.1 µl per 250 ng DNA)
 - 1,000 ng DNA
 - Nuclease-free water up to 10 µl
- The protocol can be scaled for larger reactions
- Incubate on Thermocycler as follows:
 - 42°C for x mins: Time depends on fragment size, with the standard protocol being 4 mins for >60 kb DNA sheared down to ~20-30 kb
 - 65°C for 5 mins: Inactivation of the enzyme

2.2.3 Following each shearing step, evaluate DNA size and distribution using the TapeStation or appropriate analysis method. Repeat shearing as needed until the desired size is reached.

2.2.4 If a significant number of shorter fragments are present, proceed with short fragment elimination using one of the methods specified in 1.3.4.

3. Modifications to ONT LSK library preparations

The following modifications have been made for the Oxford Nanopore LSK library preparation protocols for the PromethION flow cell.

[Ligation Sequencing Kit V14 \(SQK-LSK114\)](#)

Modifications:

3.1 Input DNA

- DNA input for the reactions is 300-500 fmol based on the mean size distribution reading from the TapeStation analysis.

3.2 FFPE repair and end prep

- For this step, the LSK and NBD protocols are similar and can be modified based on the input DNA concentration and volume. For samples with high-concentration the 50% LSK or NBD end-prep and polishing protocols can be used, while the normal LSK procedure is followed after the first bead-cleanup step.

Library building	LSK	LSK (50%)	NBD
<i>End prep and polishing</i>			
DNA	200-500 fmol (maximum 48 µl)	200-500 fmol (maximum 24 µl)	200-500 fmol (maximum 12 µl)
DNA CS (optional)	1 µl	1 µl	1 µl
Water	Up to 48 µl	UP to 24 µl	Up to 12 µl
Total	48 µl	24 µl	12 µl
NEBNext FFPE DNA Repair Buffer	3.5 µl	1.75 µl	0.875 µl
3.5 µl Ultra II End-prep Reaction Buffer	3.5 µl	1.75 µl	0.875 µl
2 µl NEBNext FFPE DNA Repair Mix	2 µl	1 µl	0.5 µl
Ultra II End-prep Enzyme Mix	3 µl	1.5 µl	0.75 µl
Total	60 µl	30 µl	15 µl

- The incubation step can be extended up to 30 min.
 - Incubate the FFPE/End preparation step at 20°C for 15-30 min.
 - Denature at 65°C for 5 min.

3.3 FFPE/End preparation Agencourt bead cleanup

- Bead cleanup volumes must be modified based on the total volume for the relevant FFPE/End preparation reaction.
 - The beads to reaction volume ratio is **1 beads : 1 reaction volume**.
 - To bind the DNA to the beads, incubate for 15 min at 25°C (RT) on a Hula mixer.

Hula mixer settings:

- **Orbital:** Off
 - **Reciprocal:** 45 degrees for 3 seconds
 - **Vibro/Pause:** 1 degree for 1 second
 - **Time:** 15 min
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- Elute DNA based on the requirement of the following step in the protocol.
 - For a full LSK and 50% LSK reaction, elute in 61 µl of water.

3.4 Native adapter ligation

Adapter Ligation	LSK
Pooled barcoded sample OR end-prepped DNA	60 µl
Ligation Adapter (LA)	5 µl (LA)
Ligation Buffer (LNB)	25 µl
NEBNext Quick T4 DNA Ligase	10 µl
Total	100 µl

- Extend the incubation step to incubate for 30 min at 25°C.

3.5 Adapter ligation bead cleanup

- Beads
 - Bead cleanup volumes must be modified based on the total volume for the NA/LA ligation reaction.
 - The ratio of beads to reaction volume is **0.4 beads : 1 reaction volume**
- To bind the DNA to the beads, incubate for 15 min at 25°C (RT) on a Hula mixer with settings in 3.3..
- To elute the library, incubate on the Thermomixer for 30 min at 37°C.

4. Modifications to ONT NBD library preparations

The following modifications have been made for the Oxford Nanopore NBD library preparation protocol for the PromethION flow cell.

[Native Barcoding Kit 24 V14 \(SQK-NBD114.24\)](#)

Modifications:

- 4.1 Input DNA:
- 300-500 fmol based on the mean size distribution reading from the TapeStation analysis and the number of samples to be pooled.
- 4.2 FFPE repair and end prep
- For this step, the LSK and NBD protocols are similar and can be modified based on the input DNA concentration and volume. For lower sample concentrations the 50% LSK or full LSK end-prep and polishing protocols can be used. Following the first bead cleanup step with elution in 10 μ l, the normal NBD library preparation method can be followed.

Library building	LSK	LSK (50%)	NBD
<i>End prep and polishing</i>			
DNA	200-500 fmol (maximum 48 μ l)	200-500 fmol (maximum 24 μ l)	200-500 fmol (maximum 12 μ l)
Water	Up to 48 μ l	UP to 24 μ l	Up to 12 μ l
Total	48 μl	24 μl	12 μl
NEBNext FFPE DNA Repair Buffer	3.5 μ l	1.75 μl	0.875 μ l
3.5 μ l Ultra II End-prep Reaction Buffer	3.5 μ l	1.75 μl	0.875 μ l
2 μl NEBNext FFPE DNA Repair Mix	2 μ l	1 μl	0.5 μ l
Ultra II End-prep Enzyme Mix	3 μ l	1.5 μl	0.75 μ l
Total	60 μl	30 μl	15 μl

- The incubation step can be extended up to 30 min.
 - Incubate the FFPE/End preparation step at 20°C for 15-30 min.
 - Denature at 65°C for 5 min.

4.3 FFPE/End preparation Agencourt bead cleanup

- Bead cleanup volumes must be modified based on the total volume for the relevant FFPE/End preparation reaction.
 - The beads to reaction volume ratio is **1 beads : 1 reaction volume**.
 - To bind the DNA to the beads, incubate for 15 min at 25°C (RT) on a Hula mixer with settings as in 3.3.
- Elute DNA based on the requirement of the following step in the protocol.
 - For NBD, elute in 10 µl nuclease-free water.

4.4 Barcode adapter ligation

The barcode adapter ligation follows the ONT protocol for reaction volumes.

- Incubate with Barcodes – extend the incubation step to incubate for 60 min at 25°C.

4.5 Barcode adapter ligation cleanup

- To bind the DNA to the beads, incubate for 30 min at 25°C (RT) on a Hula mixer with settings as in 3.3.
- Elute beads in nuclease-free water and incubate for 30 min at 37°C on the Thermomixer.

4.6 Native Adapter ligation

- NBD – follow original protocol for reaction volumes.
- Extend the incubation step to incubate for 30 min at 25°C.

4.7 Native Adapter bead cleanup

- To bind the DNA to the beads, incubate for 15 min at 25°C (RT) on a Hula mixer with settings as in 3.3.
- To elute the library, incubate for 30 min at 37°C on the Thermomixer.